

Early Identification of Low-Grade Acute Radiation Dermatitis Using *In Vivo* Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) Images of Human Head and Neck

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ABSTRACT

Radiation therapy remains an essential component of cancer treatment, with nearly 50% of cancer patients receiving radiation therapy at some point during the course of their illness. Of those, the vast majority experience some form of acute radiation dermatitis (ARD) or radiation-induced skin injury. ARD results in significant discomfort, restriction of daily activities, overall decrease in the quality of life and even cessation of the necessary radiation therapy with detrimental survival effects. Unfortunately, research into the causes and possible management strategies for ARD is hindered by the lack of biomarkers for the quantitative assessment of the early changes associated with the condition. This study provides the basis to identify low grade ARD, using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) images with the extraction of conventional image intensity and novel features. Twenty-two patients were imaged twice each week until the end of their radiation treatment resulting in 1487 images. The severity of the cases was graded by an expert oncologist. The preliminary results of various machine learning (ML) classifiers have shown that an LDA based approach provided the best performance, separating normal skin from very early ARD, with an accuracy of 85%.

1. INTRODUCTION

Acute radiation dermatitis (ARD) is a disease that appears in the majority of cancer patients as a side effect of radiation therapy. The complaints vary from erythema to moist or dry desquamation [1,2], which result in significant discomfort, restriction of daily activities, overall decrease in the quality of life (QoL) and even cessation of the necessary radiotherapy with detrimental effects [3]. Despite various studies reporting prevention or treatment of ARD, as well as guidelines published in 2013 [4], there is no standard therapy or consensus on the optimal management of the condition. Research into the causes and possible management strategies for ARD is further hindered by the lack of biomarkers for the quantitative assessment of the early changes associated with the condition. OCT is well suited for the evaluation of ARD since it can perform imaging at a resolution approaching that of histopathology (~10 μm) in real-time, does not require any contact with the patient's already-injured skin and its penetration depth (~ 2 mm) allows the visualization of the skin's diagnostically important layers such as the stratum corneum and top layer of the epidermis. In dermatology, researchers have investigated the diagnostic ability of OCT, *in vivo*, for the evaluation of basal cell carcinomas, psoriasis, allergic dermatitis and detection of radiation effects on mouse skin [5-8]. In all cases, the sensitivity and specificity reached the ranges of 80% to 96%. However, even skilled observers find it very challenging to evaluate OCT images by visual inspection alone [9]. To alleviate this problem, studies attempted to extract various features from OCT images, including intensity- and texture- based features [10,11]. Recently our team extracted features from the OCT data leading to biomarkers correlating to tissue abnormalities. These novel features include group velocity dispersion, scatterer size (corresponding mainly to cell nucleus size) and index of refraction which are affected by and reflect biochemical changes of disease [12-16]. In this study, *in vivo* head and neck OCT images, from patients undergoing radiation therapy, were collected during the course of their treatment and evaluated using a fully automated algorithm for image segmentation and feature extraction. Machine learning classifiers were utilized to differentiate normal skin from early ARD.

2. METHODOLOGY

A. Image and Data Processing

The OCT images were collected using a swept source OCT system with a center wavelength of 1300 nm, an axial resolution of 10 μm and an A-Scan rate of 40 kHz. The study was performed at the German Oncology Center (GOC), Limassol, Cyprus. For this first proof-of-concept, six male and female volunteers (>18 years old) with head and neck cancers scheduled to undergo radiation therapy at the GOC were enrolled after bioethics approval. Exclusion criteria include patients with disabilities, pregnant women, patients with prior radiation therapy at the area of examination (last six months), children, and patients with autoimmune diseases. After informed consent, a predefined area at the irradiated side of the neck of the subjects, was imaged with OCT. Six images were acquired, every 1 cm, to cover the region from the mandibular angle to the clavicle. A photograph of the same area was also taken with a digital camera. The imaging was repeated prior

to every radiation therapy session, twice per week, until the end of their therapy, resulting in a dataset of 1487 images. During each visit, the patient's ARD grade, at the same six positions imaged, was noted.

B. Feature Extraction

Automated algorithms were developed to segment the images, into stratum corneum and epidermis layers, and extract image features from the OCT images of all patients. The features included: (i) *First order intensity statistics*: Various first order statistical features of the intensity distribution extracted from predefined neighborhoods of each image including the mean, standard deviation, variance, skewness, median, kurtosis, min, max; (ii) *Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)*: The four main features of the GLCM, which quantitatively describe perceptual texture properties, calculated: Correlation, contrast, homogeneity and energy; (iii) *Novel feature – Group Velocity Dispersion (GVD)*: Measurement of the GVD *in vivo* performed using the speckle degradation method [15]. Changes in dispersion, a measure of the variation of the index of refraction of a material as a function of the wavelength of light, can be indicative of biochemical variations caused by the disease; (iv) *Novel feature – Scatterer Size (SS)*: The mean SS estimated using Mie Theory and the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative (COD) of the OCT spectrum, obtained from a frequency transformation [14]. (v) *Fractal Dimension (FD)*: Calculation of fractal dimension from predefined neighborhoods of each image using box counting method [11]. For each extracted feature, its statistics over the entire image were calculated (mean, median, variance, standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness, sum, minimum, maximum) resulting in 1454 features for every image.

C. Feature Selection and Classification

Feature selection and optimization was performed in an effort to choose the features that result in the best classification accuracy and can act as possible early ARD biomarkers. This process began with ranking features in order of significance. Prior to the classification, the final dataset, which included the most significant features, was normalized. Due to the fact that the dataset was imbalanced, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was utilized to increase the data points and avoid overfitting issues that can occur due to a minority class. Various classifiers were utilized to identify the approach that provided the best accuracy. The performance was verified using leave-one-patient-out cross-validation, to avoid introducing any bias to the results.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows an example of *in vivo* head and neck OCT images from the same patient at four different time points during radiation therapy. Every week six OCT images acquired from the same position (Week 1, white lines) along with a photo of the patient's skin. Below of every photo are the OCT images illustrating how challenging it would be to classify each by visual inspection alone, as it is very challenging to distinguish the differences in images from different weeks of therapy and detect the grade of ARD at early stages.

Figure 1. *In vivo* head and neck OCT images of different weeks of radiation therapy. The horizontal white lines of the first week photo show the spots where the OCT images acquired and below there is a preview of the corresponding OCT images used for the classification.

The regions of the stratum corneum and epidermis of each image were used to extract the features described above. The window size was 202 x 11 pixels (0.15 x 0.11 mm) for the stratum corneum region and 336 x 11 pixels (0.25 x 0.11 mm) for the epidermis region. Fourteen first and second order intensity statistics of the stratum corneum along with the GVD and SS from the epidermis appeared to be the most significant for the classification.

A Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier was utilized for normal vs early ARD classification, showing very promising results with a sensitivity of 86%, specificity of 77% and accuracy of 85%. The classification performance was verified using a leave-one-patient-out-cross validation approach.

Table 1 Classification results for Normal vs Skin with early ARD using leave-one image out-cross-validation

NR vs ARD	Sensitivity [%]	Specificity [%]	Accuracy [%]	AUC
LDA	86	77	85	0.83
k-NN	73	70	77	0,71
NB	80	63	78	0,72
SVM	83	64	80	0,73
DT	78	56	76	0,64

4. CONCLUSIONS

Given the preliminary results presented in this study, the automated algorithm proposed could be further developed to perform *in vivo* early detection and classification of ARD in patients undergoing radiation therapy. Using machine learning with LDA, the algorithm could distinguish normal skin tissue from early ARD with an accuracy of 85%, sensitivity of 86% and specificity of 77%. Although, these results are very promising, further evaluation is required, with a larger number of images from more patients, in order to optimize the segmentation and classifier models and, also, introduce deep learning. This work has the potential to be developed into a system that can be used for effective computer aided diagnosis of ARD at the early stage that could help guide both the management of the disease but, also, much-needed future research and significantly impact patient prognosis and quality of life.

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